

Exploring the Three-Tier Identity of Garhjats in Odisha

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ABSTRACT

In the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, new academic histories were produced as a part of the colonial modernist agenda, emphasising state-centric histories, that includes dynasties, kings, and royal changes. Such a scheme of history deals with war, conquest, the nature of political dominance, state structures and changes in them, and attempts to privilege a small section of elites living within such structures. Ordinary people were excluded from this kind of historical trend. Conversely, during the early 20th century, Odisha's princely kingdoms created many local histories that contested imperial viewpoints and highlighted the significance of cultural history. These histories systematically documented individuals' beliefs, folklore, mythology, legends, and daily rituals. As a result of legal disputes regarding their identities, alliances, and land ownership, royal families and dynasties sought to document their historical accounts to gain legitimacy from the colonial authorities. Following the academic model of colonial historiography, historical legends were used to recreate dynastic glories. They also included Thakur, Thakurani, rituals, and clan traditions in their regal chronicles. In this research paper, an attempt has been made to identify the three identities of garhjats from these histories: trans-local, sub-regional, and pan-Indian.

Keywords: *Garhjats, Identity, Sub-regional Pan-Indian, Tans-local, Vernacular Histories.*

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Introduction

Todar Mall, Akbar's revenue minister, divided Odisha into two parts, *Mughalbandi* and *Garhjat*, for better administrative management. *Mughalbandi*, the coastal region of Odisha with flat, rich terrain, was directly under the Mughal administration, whereas *garhjat* was ruled by local chieftains (Rajas) in a bleak and mountainous territory. *Garhjat* chieftains pay an annual tribute to the Mughals in exchange for feudation. After the Marathas, the East India Company and the British Crown regulated this system.

“The feudatory states of Orissa are known under several names: their original name was *garhjat* (fort born) Mahalas, and during the Mughal rule, they were termed as Zamindars; under British rule, they became first known as Tributary Mahalas, then as Feudatory states throughout the later part of the nineteenth and early part of the twentieth centuries and finally as princely states during the last decades before independence.”ⁱ During the Second Anglo-Maratha War, the East India Company occupied the *Mughalbandi* region of Odisha, expelling the Marathas in 1803. There were 29 tributary estates at that time.ⁱⁱ After the possession of Odisha, 13 *garhjat* were merged with *Mughalbandi* and came directly under British rule, and the remaining 16 *garhjat* became British tributary states.ⁱⁱⁱ The East India Company ruled all of Odisha after the Maratha army lost the third Anglo-Maratha war in 1818. Once the East India Company took over the *garhjat* empire, 26 feudatory or tributary states paid a fixed payment. After India gained independence, on January 1st, 1948, 25 *garhjats* out of 26 were incorporated into Odisha. After signing the merger treaty in October 1948, Mayurbhanj became part of Odisha on January 1, 1949. Singhbhum district's Seraikela and Kharsawan, originally part of Odisha, became part of Bihar on May 18, 1948.

These states had no legitimate history, and the feudatory states were never brought under the central government. Initially, aboriginal tribes of numerous tribal groups lived in these highly forested areas and fought among others. According to regional tales, Rajputs from North and Central India came to Puri on pilgrimage and founded their kingdoms in Odisha's hinterlands. The British Paramount Power never intervened in these governments' internal administrations since they recognised its suzerainty. These states' kings ruled and developed them as they saw fit.^{iv} These states covered an area of 28664 square miles and, by 1930, had an annual income of 10128237 and paid a tribute of Rs. 96449 to the British Paramountcy.^v

Trans Local Characteristics of Garhjats

Accounts of ruling houses in feudatory states, their tutelary deities, local traditions and histories, royal chronicles, or *Rajavamsavalis* (dynastic chronicles) represent fascinating subregional identities with significant vernacular accounts. The local legends about the Rajas, the tutelary deities, and their devotees form an essential part of the thematic approach of these histories. The influence of *thakurani* in areas and their extraordinary impact on the formation and construction of their patron dynasties, tribes, and local and sub-regional identities are exciting features that can be gleaned from these histories. As this local tradition and legendary discourse moved from oral to written histories, the use of the legend in the vernacular began to increase. These vernacular histories promoted the memory of the past separately from the canonical form or academic histories. These accounts are sometimes considered traditional within the core structure of modern academic history.^{vi}

Legends such as the Ranpur king worshipping a flat, round rock on the Maninag hill, identified as Maninageswari^{vii} (Lady of the Jewel Serpent). Moreover, the Sonapur king Lokavighraha or Tustikar, who worshipped *Stambheswari* (Lady of the Pillar), illustrates the integration of the most potent tutelary deities of tribal origin into Hinduism. Similarly, the *garhjat* chronicles describe the dynastic accounts of establishing their kingdoms and capitals and integrating tutelary deities or village deities (*grama Devatas*) into the royal pantheon.^{viii} Legendary accounts of the Baramba and Dhenkanal *garhjat* reveal that the tribesmen and women sacrificed themselves to protect the honour of their respective dynasties on the condition of being worshipped after the sacrifice. After such sacrifices, they were revered as *shaheed* (martyr) *Istadevatas* or tutelary deities in the form of an unhewn stone at the gate of the palace of the states.^{ix}

According to an early twentieth-century legend on Baramba, Hatakesvar Rout, the legendary founder of the Baramba dynasty, was met by a pregnant Sabara (tribal) woman near his 'future capital,' and she narrated the wonders associated with that place. After hearing about such a future, Hatakesvar replied to the woman and said that he would cut off her head and worship her as *Thakurani*. There are similar legends about Dhenkanal and Banki. Dhenka Sabra's head was worshipped outside the palace gate of Dhenkanal, while the

head of Dhobei Guru (a washerman, a low-caste Hindu) was worshipped in the old fort of Banki.^x A Nayagarh folklore involves Bauri Thakurani. According to mythology, Baghel brothers Suryamani Singh and Chandramani Singh conquered the ninth and eighth Garh to create Nayagarh and Athgarh. Suryamani killed a tiger, which caused trouble in Ralaba Garh. He was amazed to see a baby strolling with her mother. When asked, the mother did not respond. She disappeared when the king attacked her with a sword and said, “I am Bauri thakurani and am the presiding deity here, and your descendants will rule the kingdom for generations after setting up a state in the name of nine fortresses called Nabadurga (Nayagarh), and from today onwards, you will worship me as a tutelary deity. That made Bauri thakurani the *Istadevata* of Nayagarh *garhjat*.^{xi}

Other stories associated with *thakurani* of tribal origin include Maninageswari of Ranpur, Baramba or Bada Amba (The Great Mother) of Bhatarika, Charchika of Banki, Hingula of Talcher and Samaleswari of Sambalpur, who represent the family of *Astmatrikas* (Eight Mothers). Legendary stories of such goddesses are found in other feudatory states.^{xii}

The legends associated with them point to their existence long before they were discovered by their founder-patron dynasties in extraordinary circumstances outside the ‘capital.’ These were later recognised as tutelary deities and elevated to a central position in the empire’s royal pantheon. Another feature was that these tutelary deities were worshipped by tribal or low caste priests wrapped in cloth and had features like silver eyes. They evoked a sense of awe and wonder and considered the place somewhat dangerous to occupy fully.^{xiii} As part of the patron dynasties’ reunification measures, they began to be presented as ‘mobile images’ (*chalanti pratima*), mainly as bronze idols of Durga-Mahishasurmardini, worshipped by *rajguru* (royal priest). During the annual Durga Puja, the ‘mobile images’ are taken to their place of origin along with the king and the king’s priest. Such an event not only symbolises the moment when the origin (field) of the tutelary goddess becomes a site of royal performance but also validates a ritual bond between the king and the people participating in the performance.^{xiv}

Along with these tribal tutelary deities, powerful deities like Khila Munda of Ranpur, Mahakali on the Baramba border with Narsinghpur state, and Tarini of Ghatgaon on the Keonjhar state border represent the *thakuranis* of state

borders and interior regions who became less prominent in the royal pantheon. Since these goddesses originate from remote parts of the kingdoms, their devotees bring them to the royal palace for Durga Puja, separately from Ashtamitrika. These annual visits, ritual bonds, and royal court integration with these tribes legitimised the ruler's grip over the hinterland and isolated tribes. These mechanisms helped the empire integrate socially and politically and develop different traditions and subregional identities.^{xv}

Jagannath: Trans-Regional identity of Garhjats

An intriguing facet of the Jagannath tradition was the reciprocal association between Puri and *garhjats* in Odisha. Herman Kulke views incorporation of kingship into the cult and vice versa as a significant development in the context of Orissan kingship, as it served as a primary means of legitimisation.^{xvi} Jagannathism spread when the Ganga dynasty founded the first medieval Odisha empire in the twelfth century A.D. The kingdom and Jagannath cult were linked by the construction of the massive Jagannath temple, which captivated Odisha. The Gajapati kings eventually used Gangas' acknowledgement of Jagannath as Raja of Odisha (King of the Empire) and his declaration as his *Raut* (deputy) and *Putra* (son) in the thirteenth century for legitimation. The Odisha monarchs needed support from the dense forests and steep terrain because they couldn't rule them. After feudatory states developed in these hinterlands, the kings of Puri or Khurda recognised them to assert their power. These kings paid tribute to the kings of Puri and Khurda and provided military aid during wars. In return, the king of *garhjat* got some special privileges in the service of Jagannath, like "the Rajas of neighbouring Ranpur, for instance, had the privilege of the 'dagger and sword service' (*churi-khanda seva*), carrying these weapons whenever Jagannath proceeds ritually for hunting. Particularly fascinating is the hierarchy of these privileges. Thus, only a few princely visitors got permission to use a *Chamara* whisk with a golden handle in front of Lord Jagannath, whereas others had to use a fan with a silver handle. A particular criterion of distinction was the display of one's royal paraphernalia not only in Puri but also onto the outer Lion's Gate or even the inner gate of the temple. An additional exceptional opportunity entailed the visitation of the female members of the royal dynasties of *garhjats* within the sacred confines after the departure of devotees and religious officials. Most likely greatest was the privilege to act during the visit of Puri as an administrator (*pariksa*) or even

head administrator (*adipariksa*) of the Jagannath temple”.^{xvii} These exceptional privileges were meant to reinforce the Khurda kings’ vulnerable position. Instead, it boosted the *garhjat* rulers’ reputation. They participate in Jagannath ceremonies and enjoy special benefits from the Gajapatis, Odisha’s highest authority, elevating their position in their culture and competing with other *garhjat* states.^{xviii}

The Puri or Khurda and *garhjat* seat relationship disseminated Jagannath culture throughout Odisha. All Odia-speaking people believed that the Puri or Khurda rulers became absolute kings with the new Jagannath shrines, which helped build Jagannath temples in other parts of Odisha. Like the traditions of Ranpur, King Uddhav Singh Narendra (1494-1514) rode to Puri daily to meet Jagannath. The King couldn’t go to Puri one day due to river flooding. The next day, King Uddhav Singh visited Puri and sat near Kalpabat for seven days. At Nighttime, Lord Jagannath appeared in his dream and instructed him to build a temple in his state. Gajapati Prataprudra Dev had a similar dream. He handed Uddhav the Gundicha temple’s Madham idol and bestowed him with the title Narendra. Later, Uddhav Singh Narendra built Ranpurgarh’s Jagannath temple.^{xix} It helped the Gajpatis to exercise their authority over *garhjat*. The political power of the Rajas of Puri and Khurda, rather than declining, became more powerful during the rule of Afghans because the Rajas of *garhjat* recognised their authority, and Lord Jagannath was at the centre of this legitimation.

1. The Rajas of Puri or Khurda legitimated as the King of Odisha. Subsequently, they claimed an imperial status among the Hindu Rajas of India by declaring themselves as the *Adisevaka*, *Rauta*, and *Putra* of Lord Jagannath.
2. The cult of Jagannath resulted in vertical political mobility. The seats of Puri or Khurda, situated at the apex of vertical mobility and *garhjat*, were arranged according to a specific hierarchy.
3. Lord Jagannath held the status of a supreme and national deity in both Mughalbandi and *garhjat* regions, increasing horizontal mobility within religion, culture, and society in Odisha.

To enhance their status and expand their royal pantheon beyond its tribal heritage, the kings and Maharajas of the *Garhjat* Mahal undertook the drive in favour of Kshatriyasation and Hinduization.^{xx} Kshatriyasation includes

various attempts by *garhjat* rulers to raise their social status by imitating the symbols of Hinduization and by claiming the status of Kshatriyas. While transforming the *garhjat* Mahalas into feudatory states, the *garhjat* rulers tried to create a veritable centre by emulating or competing with the seats of Khurda and Puri Gajapatis. Therefore, the kings of *garhjat* made plans and established new capitals, in which a new *Sashana* village was established with Brahmin inhabitants (a road like Puri *Badadanda* in the middle of the village and houses on both sides of the road). In addition, temples were established for their Hinduized *thakuranis* and other Hindu divinities, especially a temple dedicated to Jagannath, and most importantly, the *Rajprasad* (royal palace) was built near the *Badadanda* and Jagannath temples. In competition with the Raja of Khurda, the rulers of *garhjat Mahal* started building Hindu temples in their capitals.^{xxi} The *garhjat* kings ultimately accepted the annual car festival of Jagannath, known as *Rath Yatra*, while diverting their attention from their renowned tribal *thakuranis*. The *garhjats* states demonstrated their national identity by constructing Jagannath temples while incorporating regional deities to reflect their subregional and trans-local identities. Like the King of Puri, the Rajas of *garhjats* participated in meaningful religious ceremonies such as the *Cherapahara* during the chariot festival of Lord Jagannath. The rulers of *garhjat* emulated the way of life of the kings of Khurda and Puri, which was evident in their daily activities. To distinguish themselves from the commoners and assert their royal status, the kings of *garhjats* employed specific vernacular syntaxes commonly utilised by the Gajapatis of Puri, such as *Nagara* or *Uasa* (referring to the king's residence or palace), *Ranishinapur* (referring to the residence of the Queen), *Manohibije* (referring to the act of eating), *Pahdibije* (referring to the act of sleeping), *Shuleibije* (referring to the act of using the toilet), *Kathilagi* (referring to the act of brushing one's teeth), and *Poili* (referring to a maid). *Rangamahal* (a residential structure constructed entirely of marble). The *Khatami* (regal attire worn by monarchs), while the *Mardanabije* refers to the application of oil massage on the body of a king, typically lasting from 8 am to 1 pm. Additionally, the *beharan*, *khidmat*, and *khilamatiya* denote the roles of domestic servants.

Pan-Indian Identities of Garhjats

Historical accounts suggest that most *garhjat* states were founded by Kshatriya Rajputs who undertook a pilgrimage to Puri and subsequently

established their dominion in the rural areas of Odisha. It is widely acknowledged that the Gajapatis held direct dominion over the plains. In contrast, the hinterlands of Odisha, characterised by their rough terrain and dense forests, were not subject to their direct governance. From the ninth to the thirteenth century, the *garhjat* region was governed by minor indigenous leaders. Subsequently, the Rajputs or Kshatriyas, who embarked on a pilgrimage to Puri, established their dominion in Odisha's surrounding regions. The Rajputs or Kshatriyas, who were outsiders, established eleven kingdoms, namely Nayagarh, Athmallik, Banai, Mayurbhanj, Narsinghpur, Ranpur, Patna, Tigiria, Talcher, Nilagiri, and Pallhara *garhjat*. Additionally, the brothers of the kings of the states above, or rajas of neighbouring dynasties, founded four kingdoms: Khandpara, Dasapalla, Kendujhar, and Sonepur. The regions of Bamanda, Baud, Dhenkanal, Kalahandi, Gangpur, and Athgarh were founded by Kshatriyas, either appointed by the King of Odisha or chosen from the locality. Before the emergence of *garhjat*, the Gajapatis of Odisha did not receive any form of taxation or assistance from the surrounding hinterlands governed by various local chieftains. Hence, the Gajapatis did not raise any objections to establishing a considerably large and fortified state by external entities in the Odisha hinterlands.

Histories written by various *garhjat* dynasties in the late medieval period, such as the Ranpur dynasty chronicles, provide information on the origins of the dynasty and its traditional deities, their relationship to the mythological history of the pan- Indian epics, and Puranic traditions. Later dynasties remain a mystery associated with its regional past. Examples are given through legends based on invented traditions. The history of these ruling houses of Odisha is linked through their enduring links with the kings of Gajapati, Lord Jagannatha, or the Rajput heroes/dynasties of Rajasthan and, like the chiefs of other provinces of India, many of the feudatory chiefs and Zamindars of Odisha claim to be Rajputs.^{xxii} The monarchs of the Patnagarh dynasty asserted their lineage to Prithviraj Chauhan, a member of the Chauhan clan. According to legend, this clan of Delhi fell after the defeat and death of Prithviraj Chauhan by Muhammad Ghori in the Battle of Tirori. Later, some branches of this clan established many small kingdoms in Rajasthan and North India. One of these states is the state of Mainpur. The Chauhan king of Mainpur was defeated and killed while resisting the Muslim attack. His three queens, who had already given birth to a son, committed sati. However, since

the fourth queen was pregnant, some scholars advised her to refrain from committing sati. To save his life, he secretly reached West Odisha with the help of some followers and established the Chauhan clan here.^{xxiii} Similarly, the Kalahandi king claimed his ancestry from the Naga dynasty, the Baudh king as Bhanjas, Gangapur from the Parmar dynasty, Bannai from the Kadamba dynasty, Bamanda from the Ganga dynasty, Sambalpur Patnagarh and Sonepur from the Chauhan dynasty.^{xxiv}

Interestingly, in a historiographical endeavour, the respective states produced histories to recreate or invent local, regional, and pan-Indian traditions. Through these histories, they tried to legitimise their dynastic, genealogical history and sacred, local, and sub-regional identities and demonstrated their superiority over other states. Hermann Kulke explores the history of the Ranpur dynasty and presents three interrelated concepts of the past. In this sequence, the states have reproduced their past as pan-Indian, a local construct of the regional past, and a commemorative trans-local past. Kulke notes in Ranpur's biography that the genealogical histories depict two distinct genealogical processes and prior ideas. One link reflected Indian and regional identity, the other local and tribal. One idea was to link the myth's pan-Indian and trans-regional nature to the regional and pan-Indian realm through mythology's constant localisation. The chronicle's storytelling method shows universalisation and localisation.^{xxv}

Details of Garhjats in Odisha ^{xxvi}								
S. L. N. o	Name of the Garhjat	Area (In Sq. Miles)	Population			Income As per 1939	Geographical location	Royal Emblem
			1891	1901	1939			
1	Atgarh	168	36603	43784	50148	148000	Adjacent to Cuttack district.	Radha Krishna
2	Athmalik	730	31605	40753	64276	217000	Adjacent to Angul of Cuttack district.	Kadamba flower
3	Bamra	1988	101170	123378	151259	424000	Nearest to the district of Sambalpur.	Sankha
4	Baramba	142	32526	38260	46689	97000	Adjacent to the Banki subdivision of Cuttack district.	heraldic dog-tiger

5	Baud	1264	89551	88250	135248	321000	Adjacent to Angul of Cuttack district.	Peacock
6	Bonai	1296	32120	38277	80144	176000	Nearest to the district of Sambalpur.	Peacock
7	Daspalla	568	45597	51987	42650	120000	Ancient to the district of Ganjam	Peacock
8	Dhenkanal	1436		273662	284328	531000	Adjacent to district of Cuttack.	Fish
9	Gangpur	2492	191440	238896	356388	508000	16 Miles from Jharsuguda station	deity Jagdala
10	Hindol	312	37973	47180	48897	126000	Adjacent to Angul of Cuttack district.	Dagger
11	Kalahandi	3745		350529	513716	625000	Adjacent to the district of Sambalpur.	Cobra
12	Keonjhar	3096	248101	285758	460647	979000	Adjacent to Jajpur Road station.	Peafowl
13	Khandapara	244	63287	69450	77930	148000	Adjacent to the Banki subdivision of the Cuttack district	Tiger's head
14	Mayurbhanj	4243	532238	610383	889603		It borders Balasore in the south, Medinapur in the east, and Singhbhum district in the north.	Peacock
15	Narasingpur	199			40882	111000	Adjacent to Angul of Cuttack district.	Scorpion
16	Nayagarh	590		140779	142399	396000	Adjacent to the Khurda sub-division of Puri district.	Tiger's head
17	Nilagiri	284	56198	66460	68598	173000	Adjacent to the district of Balasore.	Corolla flower
18	Pallahara	452	19700	22351	27975	79000	The nearest British territory is Angul.	Cobra

19	Patna	2511		277748	566924	2941000	Adjacent to the district of Sambalpur.	Chakra
20	Rairakhhol	833	In 1866 25000	26888	35710	87000	Adjacent to Angul and Sambalpur	Sankha Padma
21	Ranpur	203	40115	46075	47713	71000	Adjacent to the Puri district.	Sword
22	Seraikela	449			138671	334000	Adjacent to Singhbhum district of Bihar province.	
23	Sonepur	906	60000	169877	237945	492000	Adjacent to the Sambalpur district	Chakra
24	Talcher	399	52674	60432	69702	294000	Adjacent to Angul of Cuttack district	Tiger
25	Tigiria	46	20465	22625	24680	45000	Adjacent to the Banki subdivision of Cuttack district.	sastra Pancha

Conclusion

The sub-regional identity of these *garhjats* is a combination of the local Odisha (regional) and pan-Indian histories, together with their respective historical frames. These writings' immense popularity and dissemination can be attributed to their creative combination of pan-Indian, regional, and local history. This arrangement of three genealogical stages strengthens Romila Thapar's notion of compressing the past. Nevertheless, such little chronicles are less appreciated in modern canonical histories. Such historiographical interventions extend the meaningful engagement of a precious treasure of local histories with modern histories.

End Notes

ⁱ H, Kulke. "The Feudatory States of Orissa: Centres out There", in edited by Hermann Kulke and Georg Berkemer, *Centres Out There? Facets of Subregional Identities in Orissa*, New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors, 2011, p. 61.

ⁱⁱ B, Das. *Orissa in Hamilton's Hindostan*, Cuttack: Utkal Union Committee, 1820, P.P. 35-92.

ⁱⁱⁱ The Sixteen states were *Mayurbhanj, Nilagiri, Angul, Athgarh, Dhenkanal, Banki, Daspalla, Nayagarh, Narasingpur, Ranpur, Talcher, Tigiria, Hindol, Sukinda, Keonjhar and Khandapara*:

Bhabani Charan Ray, *Foundations of British Orissa*, Cuttack: New Students Store, 1960, p. 76.

^{iv} H, Nanda. *Nayagarh Itihas*, Burla: Five-star Printing Press, 2006, pp. I-IV.

^v General Review of Administration of the Feudatory States of Orissa for the Year, 1930-31, p. 29.

^{vi} Kulke, H. "The Feudatory States of Orissa: Centres Out There", edited by Hermann Kulke and Georg Berkemer, *Centres Out There? Facets of Subregional Identities in Orissa*, New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors, 2011, p. 67.

^{vii} *Ibid.*, p. 62.

^{viii} *Ibid.*, p. 67.

^{ix} *Ibid.*, pp. 67-69.

^x *Ibid.*, p. 68.

^{xi} K, C, Panigrahi. "Baurirani Debinka Janan", *Nayagarh Itihas*, Puri: Hadibandhu Press, 1982, p. I. And Harihara Nanda, *Nayagarh Itihas*, Burla: Five-star Printing Press, 2006, pp. 1-4.

^{xii} H, Kulke. "The Feudatory States of Orissa: Centres Out There", edited by Hermann Kulke and Georg Berkemer, *Centres Out There? Facets of Subregional Identities in Orissa*, New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors, 2011, p. 68.

^{xiii} *Ibid.*, p. 68.

^{xiv} C, P, Nanda, "Re-provincialising the word of Deshi: Odisha as retold by its histories, Subaltern Pasts, and Transmemoration," In Edited by Chandi Prasad Nanda, Pritish Acharya and Shri Krishan, *Vernacularizing pasts, Odisha: Mahabharata to Modernity*, Delhi: Primus Books, 2022, p. 229.

^{xv} H, Kulke. "The Feudatory States of Orissa: Centres out There", edited by Hermann Kulke and Georg Berkemer, *Centres Out There? Facets of Subregional Identities in Orissa*, New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors, 2011, p. 69.

^{xvi} H, Kulke. "Early Royal Patronage of the Jagannath Cult," edited by Anncharlott Eschmann. Herman Kulke and Gaya Charan Tripathi, *The Cult of Jagannath and the Regional Tradition of Orissa*, Delhi: Manohar Publications, 1986, p. 139.

^{xvii} H, Kulke. "The Feudatory States of Orissa: Centres Out There," edited by Hermann Kulke and Georg Berkemer, *Centres Out There? Facets of Subregional Identities in Orissa*, New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors, 2011, p. 66.

^{xviii} *Ibid.*, p. 67.

^{xix} P, Mohapatra. *Kotikaibalyanath Mahaprabhu Shree Jagannath*, Cuttack: Satyanarayan Book Store, 2019, pp. 559-560.

^{xx} H, Kulke. "The Feudatory States of Orissa: Centres Out There," edited by Hermann Kulke and Georg Berkemer, *Centres Out There? Facets of Subregional Identities in Orissa*, New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors, 2011, p. 70.

^{xxi} *Ibid.*, pp. 70–71.

^{xxii} Motte, T. *Asiatic Annual Register*, 1799, pp. 73-74. And Banerji, R. D. *History of Orissa: From the earliest to the British period*, Calcutta: Prabasi Press, 1931, pp. 421-427.

^{xxiii} B, B, Mishra. *Dakshina Kosala (Paschima Odisha) Sankshipta Itihasa*, Sambalpur: Menaka Prakashani, 2003, pp. 51-52.

^{xxiv} *Ibid.*, pp. 51–80.

^{xxv} C, P, Nanda. "Re-provincialising the word of Deshi: Odisha as retold by its histories, Subaltern Pasts, and Transmemoration," In Edited by Chandi Prasad Nanda, Pritish Acharya and Shri Krishan, *Vernacularizing pasts, Odisha: Mahabharata to Modernity*, Delhi: Primus Books, 2022m p. 225.

^{xxvi} L.E.B. Cobden Ramsay, *Bengal Gazetteers: Feudatory States of Orissa*, Calcutta: Bengal Secretariat Book Depot, 1910. And Enquiry Committee Report, Orissa States, Bombay: All Indian States Peoples Conference, 1939.